

CCSDS 123.0-B-2 COMPRESSION STANDARD CROSS-VALIDATION AND FUZZING

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Abstract

The Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems requires candidate standards to complete a ‘cross-validation’ process in which two or more independent implementations of the candidate standard are shown to produce equivalent results. Four different groups each created an independent implementation during the development of the CCSDS 123.0-B-2 standard for multispectral and hyperspectral image compression, and their respective results were verified to produce identical results through extensive use of fuzzing techniques. This document provides a case study of the cross-validation process followed during the development of the CCSDS 123.0-B-2 standard and the role that fuzzing techniques played through this process.

Key words: CCSDS 123.0-B-2; verification; cross-validation; fuzz testing; fuzzing harness; data compression.

1. INTRODUCTION

During the development of recommended standards by the Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (CCSDS), at least two independent and interoperable prototypes or implementations must be developed and demonstrated [1]. In this document, the implementation and verification steps taken between interdependent parties are referred to as the ‘cross-validation’ process.¹

In 2019, CCSDS published the CCSDS 123.0-B-2 recommended standard titled *Low-Complexity Lossless and Near-Lossless Multispectral and Hyperspectral Image Compression* [2]. It is a moderately complex standard, in part due to its large configuration space, and its cross-validation presented major challenges in this regard. In this paper we present an atheoretical case study with an illustrative approach describing this process and share some of the insights gained during the process.

Case studies —typical of social and natural sciences— are extremely rare in the field of data compression. Yet, insight and know-how on international standardization efforts are often scarce. The European Commission describes this in [3, pp. 8–9] as: “The use of standards is growing, the importance of standardisation for the competitiveness and public good is

¹Technically, this document describes only the ‘cross-verification’ of four standard implementations, as the suitability of the standardized compression technique was already established in earlier stages of the development of the standard. However, the use of the term ‘cross-validation’ has remained for historical reasons.

undisputed, but the general awareness and training on standardisation is comparably small. There is no formal education nor vocational training on standardisation. [...] This is worrying and reflected in the overall difficulty to recruit technical experts for the standardisation development work.”

Back in early 2018, the standard definition was being finalized, and the members of the CCSDS Multispectral and Hyperspectral Data Compression working group were urged to have it cross-validated by the upcoming spring meeting that would take place in April. As the cross-validation progressed, the use of fuzzing techniques proved to be quite successful in detecting issues in the definition of the candidate standard that resulted in errors and discrepancies between independent implementations. This document, in conjunction with the internal CCSDS ‘yellow book’ for CCSDS 123.0-B-2 [4], describes that experience and shares some of the insights obtained during the standardization efforts.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. First, the cross-validation participants and implementations created are outlined in Section 2. Section 3 describes the Fuzzing techniques employed. Section 4 describes the tests that were carried out, while Section 5 summarizes the process and the lessons learned. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section 6.

2. PARTICIPANTS AND IMPLEMENTATIONS

Four independent groups participated in the CCSDS 123.0-B-2 cross-validation, each developing a separate implementation of the candidate standard and ensuring matching results.

One implementation was produced at NASA’s Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL) by Aaron Kiely, Matthew Klimesh, and Michael Cheng. A second implementation was developed at University of Dayton Research Institute (UDRI) by Brenton Sundlie. A third implementation was produced at NASA Goddard Space Flight Center (GSFC) by Mark Wong. Finally, a fourth implementation was produced at Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB) for the Centre National d’Études Spatiales (CNES) by Ian Blanes, Miguel Hernández-Cabronero, and Joan Serra-Sagristà.

Both JPL’s and UAB’s implementations included a compressor and a decompressor, and were programmed in the C language. GSFC’s implementation employed MATLAB, and also included a compressor and a decompressor. UDRI’s implementation included only a compressor and employed C++.

Participants were not allowed to share any source code or executable binaries among themselves, which necessarily required all participants to agree on a testing methodology based on test vectors. To this day, all implementations remain closed source, with CNES kindly making available a binary-only version of UAB’s implementation at [5].

3. FUZZING

Fuzzing is a technique in which pseudorandomly generated *inputs* are automatically fed to a given software with the objective of revealing software malfunctions. While it is often used in the field of cybersecurity to detect software vulnerabilities, it is also an excellent addition to software testing techniques [6].

UAB’s implementation of CCSDS 123.0-B-2 already employed fuzz testing for internal quality assurance, and these efforts were extended to generate test vectors which could be shared among the four groups. As detailed later, this use of fuzzing during the cross-validation proved remarkably useful in substantially reducing the effort required to produce test vectors, in detecting and removing software defects, and in detecting inconsistencies in the definition of the standard.

Fuzzing is usually performed through a project-independent piece of software called a *fuzzer*, which takes care of input generation and controls the execution of the tested software. In this case, American Fuzzy Lop (AFL) version 2.52b was used [7]. Like most current fuzzers, AFL is a *coverage-guided* fuzzer. I.e., it uses code coverage information obtained from executing tested inputs to automatically guide subsequent input generation, which in practice maximizes the number of tested lines of code.

To successfully apply fuzzing to a given software, a fuzzing harness is designed. A fuzzing harness is a small piece of code that glues the fuzzer to the testing program. It takes the input given by the fuzzer itself and calls the test program. A trivial fuzzing harness can be thought of as an adapter between the fuzzer and the software interfaces. However, more complex fuzzing harnesses are described below.

The use of a coverage-guided fuzzer with carefully designed test harnesses efficiently produced test vectors that covered the whole standard, i.e., ensured that every compression option was exercised.

3.1. Designing Software for Fuzz Testing

To apply fuzz testing to any software implementation, the implementation must be extremely resilient. The CCSDS 123.0-B-2 prototype was required not to crash under invalid user-provided data, regardless of its compliance with the aforementioned standard.

UAB's implementation was designed to be fuzz tested and was employed to generate the test vectors that the other implementations could verify. The following considerations were taken into account while developing the software:

- The implementation was written in strict accordance with C99 (ISO/IEC 9899:1999) and POSIX.1-2008. Undefined behavior was avoided and implementation-defined behavior was only employed if it was defined in POSIX.1-2008. UBSAN [8] was employed to detect undefined and implementation-defined behavior.
- Variables were *not* initialized to default values. Hence, it was possible to detect use of uninitialized variables with Valgrind [9] and MSAN [10]. This decision risked non-deterministic behavior due to uninitialized variable usage while in production, but it allowed detection of these errors while in development.
- Design by contract was employed in internal functions with extensive assertions through the whole code base, so that inconsistencies could be effectively triggered during fuzzing.
- External functions employed defensive calling conventions, where data was assumed to possibly be incorrect. In addition, system call errors had to be reported to callers, so that fault injection could be employed and fault detection could be verified. Libfui [11] was employed for fault injection tests.
- The implementation needed to be reasonably efficient so that the fuzzing process could reach full code coverage. Moreover, the implementation needed to operate under constrained memory limits, so that no test case consumed unreasonably large amounts of memory.
- In addition, the software development requirements set by CNES in RNC-CNES-Q-ST-80-100 [12] were taken into account.

3.2. End-to-end harness

Eleven fuzzing harnesses were employed during UAB's software development, with many of these harnesses being simple adapters stressing a particular element (e.g., compressed image header encoding and decoding routines). One of these harnesses is a comprehensive *end-to-end harness* that was designed to generate test inputs. This harness takes an input, as generated by the fuzzer, and tries to decompress it as a valid CCSDS 123.0-B-2 bitstream. If successful, it tries to recompress the decompressed image using the same configuration while ensuring the newly produced file matches the original one. Any failed comparison detects a potential error in the standard or the implementation. See Fig. 1 for a diagram of the end-to-end harness.

An exception to the previous comparison is made when the block-adaptive encoder is employed because non-compliant code selections produce decompressible bitstreams. These bitstreams are non-compliant, yet the decoder was unable to detect them. Hence, the cross-validation harness performs one additional decompression and recompression of the previously decompressed and recompressed input to detect potential errors related to code selections.

Similarly, other standard features require careful consideration. This is the case of optional header tables, which are parts of a compressed file header which may be omitted, for example, if they are constant throughout a mission. This is problematic because a decompressor needs a second input with these tables, but the fuzzer only produces one. To address this, the cross-validation harness only decodes compressed files without optional tables. It then employs the 'User-Defined Data' header field to selectively extract such tables and employs them in a subsequent decompression. In addition, the end-to-end harness also includes the testing of supplementary information tables (SIT), including their binary to plain text conversion, and successfully reproduces error limit updates and hybrid initial accumulators when files are recompressed.

3.3. Command-line harness

Another interesting fuzzing harness is the *command-line harness* that was designed to ensure a very high quality implementation.

This harness is capable of automatically producing calls to the command-line tools based on the contents of the test input. In practice, the harness is given a command-line tool and automatically learns how to invoke it and which inputs are needed to produce compressed or decompressed files.

Figure 1: The end-to-end harness. Orange lines denote comparisons the harness must pass in order not to crash.

Table 1: Actions executed by the command-line harness.

Value	Action	Description
0x00	ARGUMENT	Remove the immediately subsequent null-terminated string from the action sequence and add it to the argument list.
0x01	FILE	Add a mock file name to the argument list.
0x02	SET_STDIN	Set a mock file as the standard input stream.
0x03	CLOSE_STDOUT	Close the standard output stream.
0x04	CLOSE_STDERR	Close the standard error stream.

Table 2: Example input for the command-line harness. Command line is “lcnl_encoder f000 u8be f001 f002”.

Bytes	Description
0x02,	Tool is ‘lcnl_encoder’.
0x01,	FILE; push file name to argument list.
0x00, 0x75, 0x38,	ARGUMENT; push string 0x75, 0x38, 0x62, 0x65 (‘u8be’) to the argument list.
0x62, 0x65, 0x00,	
0x01,	FILE; push file name to argument list.
0x01,	FILE; push file name to argument list.
0x6e,	Unknown action; end of argument list construction.
0x02, 0x00, 0x00,	Contents of the first file are 0x00, 0x00, 0x02, ..., 0x01.
0x00, 0x00, 0x02,	
..., 0x01, 0x00,	
0x05, 0x85, 0x85,	Contents of the second file are 0x85, 0x85, ...
...	

(file continues)

The harness operates by processing an input as a recipe on how to compose the command line arguments for a given command-line tool. With such a harness, the coverage-guided approach of the AFL fuzzer is able to reach code paths that produce valid compressed or decompressed files.

A test input is composed of the following fields:

- (a) A one-byte field that selects the command-line tool to test (compressor, decompressor, header manipulation utility, et cetera).
- (b) A variable-length *action sequence* of bytes which controls which *actions* the harness will take to construct the command line.
- (c) A variable-length sequence of bytes incorporating the initial contents of the files that will be given to the command-line tool.

The harness starts with an empty argument list and consecutively processes each byte in the action sequence as one of the actions described in Table 1. An unknown action value signals the end of the action sequence. Afterwards, the harness proceeds to process the sequence of file contents. For each file referenced in the action sequence, the harness reads one byte. If the byte is zero, the file is not created. Otherwise, a null-terminated string is read and it is written to a mocked file (null values are escaped as two consecutive null values). Once the command line is built and files have been populated, the harness proceeds to call the command-line tool, while redirecting the opening of files to their mocked versions. See Table 2 for an example input to the end-to-end harness.

As detailed, this harness can be employed to test all command-line tools directly as would have been called by the end user. However, one further testing step is performed for command-line tools. Once a set of inputs that achieves high code coverage is obtained for the end-to-end harness, this set of inputs is fed to a modified harness that employs libfui to inject faults in system calls. I.e., the software is further tested for simulated I/O errors, insufficient memory conditions, invalid file names, etc. This is done as follows: the harness is called multiple times for each input, and for each execution a subsequent system call is made to fail. Thus, command-line tools are tested to properly handle an error in any single system call they execute for each input.

4. CROSS-VALIDATION TESTS

The tests performed during the cross-validation of CCSDS 123.0-B-2 are organized in two large fuzzing-generated test sets, and a small collection of additional handcrafted tests. Tests are described in the following subsection and are publicly available at the CCSDS Collaborative Work Environment (CWE) [13].

4.1. Test Set 1

Test Set 1 is designed to stress the configuration space of a compressor, and to thoroughly test compressor and decompressor behavior using very small synthetic test images. The end-to-end harness was subjected to 15 million executions by the AFL fuzzer to generate inputs, which were later minimized with `afl-cmin`, and are the basis of this test set. For each input that can be decompressed successfully, a test vector is created including the configuration employed and a reference decompressed image.

The test included 7946 small synthetic images (half of these had less than 1300 samples, and the largest had just over 130,000 samples). Test images had an aggregate size of 145 MBytes when uncompressed, and 1.5 MBytes when compressed.

4.2. Test Set 2

Test Set 2 complements Test Set 1 by thoroughly exercising compressors and decompressors using very large volumes of data. It was generated by using the compressor configurations produced in Test Set 1 to encode the multispectral and hyperspectral test images in the MHDC corpus [13]. The corpus includes 10 GBytes of data from over a dozen different airborne and spaceborne imagers ranging from 2 Msamples to over 200 Msamples per image.

Test Set 2 consisted of 17401 test cases for which only the configuration to be employed and the cryptographic checksum of the compressed image were provided. Test images had an aggregate size of 2.1 TBytes when uncompressed, and of 902 GBytes when compressed.

4.3. Test Set 3

A third test set was generated during the cross-validation. Test set 3 includes all test samples generated using the end-to-end harness that are not valid compressed files. I.e., files which a strict compliant decompressor should reject.

This test set was not employed for cross-validation, but is provided in the CWE for implementers interested in thoroughly stressing their implementations.

4.4. Hybrid Entropy Coder Test Image

Handcrafted tests were generated when it was necessary and possible to exhaustively test a feature. This is the case of the hybrid entropy encoder tables, which are relatively large and need to be transcribed properly into implementations. Hence, a handcrafted test image was produced. This image was designed so that all hybrid encoder codewords would be used during its compression or decompression, and thus ensuring a proper incorporation of these codeword tables.

4.5. Overflow Test Pattern Image

A second handcrafted test image was produced to detect incorrect overflows within the predictor. This image is a 32-bit equivalent to the 16-bit test pattern previously available for CCSDS 123.0-B-1 [14, 13].

The image produces large magnitudes in the accumulator register during the calculation of predicted values, and tests for accurate overflow implementations. In addition, for the sample-adaptive and hybrid encoders, the image tests all (high-entropy) variable length code parameters and triggers the unary length limit. For the block-adaptive encoder, the image triggers the all-zeros coding option repeated times.

4.6. Synthetic High Dynamic Range Image

A third handcrafted image was created to test high dynamic range behavior. CCSDS 123.0-B-2 supports image bit depths of up to 32 bits to accommodate for future instrument needs. Hence, a third handcrafted test image was produced to simulate a natural high dynamic range image. The image was created by binning an existing 16-bit AVIRIS-NG image to produce a 25-bit image that would simulate one obtained with an instrument of such a high dynamic range.

5. CROSS-VALIDATION DEVELOPMENT AND LESSONS LEARNED

This section describes the cross-validation process evolution and the lessons learned. Note, however, that as this was an exercise in complete participant observation, it is inevitably shaped by the subjective experience of the participants.

5.1. Description

The cross-validation process started early February 2018 and took up to the end of April 2018, with some additional tasks being carried out until November of the same year.

Participants had a tight schedule—set by the CCSDS meeting dates—and had to both create or complete their implementations and perform the cross-validation itself. As soon as participants had some minimally functioning implementations, even if lacking many features, they started sharing a few handcrafted test vectors. At this point, the participants had already detected five different errors in the standard text draft. Some of these errors were simple typographical mistakes, while others were related to ambiguous wording in the standard, and one was an error in a formula that would have broken backwards compatibility.

An early set of 596 fuzz-generated test vectors were then created. The test set included both valid and invalid files (later split into Test Set 1 and Test Set 3). To describe the configuration of each test vector, the binary header of a compressed file was used as an interchangeable configuration file format between the participants, without the need to agree on a different representation. Unfortunately, implementation errors and missing features made it impossible to verify any of the early test vectors. Moreover, it was soon realized by participants that implementation robustness would play a key role in the process, as these early test vectors started crashing the implementations. Anecdotally, one participant reported having a computer freeze due to a massive memory allocation when trying to decompress an invalid 6 Terasample image.

As the cross-validation progressed, many of diverging implementation behaviors were triaged and addressed. By early March it *seemed* that there were just a couple of bugs to address before implementations were stable. Two minor improvements to the standard text were introduced, and support for periodic error updating for BSQ inputs was dropped. Twelve handcrafted test images were created, with most of the groups' energy involved in fixing implementation bugs.

A test set of 2977 valid small compressed files was produced as soon as implementations started to stabilize. I.e., they stopped crashing while fuzzing. An early version of Test Set 2 was produced afterwards. Most of March was spent addressing implementation bugs, which required large amounts of energy to triage and fix, and by late March a new draft standard was circulated, including changes in SIT and required to refresh the sets of test vectors, though no major mistakes were detected in the text. Most of April was spent on efforts related to SIT and the creation of the final test vectors, and by the end of April testing was completed and the draft standard was submitted for agency review.

In October, a few changes were introduced in the standard based on Review Item Dispositions (RIDs) from the agency review process. Two changes related to SITs and one led to a small improvement to the hybrid encoder. Test vectors were rebuilt and re-verified. The cross-validation was completed.

Later in January 2019, Matthew Klimesh detected an invalid header configuration in the test vectors, where an unused header field was not set to zero, and these were rebuilt yet again. Hence, tests currently available in the CWE differ from those actually used in the cross-validation (tests and sizes reported in the previous section are accurate for the tests conducted during the cross-validation process).

Three Technical Corrigenda were issued since the standard publication. In July 2019 and August 2020, errors were detected in the Implementation Conformance Statement (ICS) annex. In February 2021, two codewords were found missing on the human-readable version of the tables. Notwithstanding, the provided binary tables were already correct.

5.2. Analysis

Virtually all the cross-validation communication was conducted through electronic mail, with more than 150 messages were exchanged. Of these, most deal with diverging implementation behaviors, while a very small portion discuss testing strategy and deal with defects found in the standard.

It took about twice as much effort to have all implementations match as the effort already spent when it seemed that a match would be close. The process was quite exhaustive and there were a very large number of defects detected and addressed. Thanks to the fuzzing approach, very convoluted issues were detected, including an identical overflow independently produced on two of the implementations.

One drawback of employing test vectors produced through fuzzing is that implementations that are not feature complete might not be reliably verified against these tests. As each test vector exercises many features at once, discarding an unsupported test vector impedes the correct testing of all the other features exercised by that test vector.

Regarding the location of the defects themselves, most of them were produced in the headers and were related to the large configuration space of the standard. In particular, SITs were very burdensome to implement and properly test. In any case, fuzzing was an excellent methodology to produce test vectors, which allowed the participants to focus their efforts in fixing bugs and forget about the time-consuming tasks of creating handcrafted tests.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This article describes the cross-validation process that was followed during the standardization of the CCSDS 123.0-B-2 recommended standard. Four different groups participated by creating four independent implementations of the standard and identical results were obtained. Several strategies were employed, the most important of which was a large set of test vectors produced by carefully designed fuzzing harnesses. The use of fuzzing greatly reduced the time spent creating test patterns and allowed the participants to focus on fixing implementation defects. This approach was capable of detecting defects derived from very complex interactions, where corner cases are easily missed. Hence, fuzzing is a highly effective tool for any algorithm development and verification process of a similar nature.

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